

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

2024

No 12

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

*Elektron nashr. 170 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 7-dekabrda ruxsat etildi.*

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:
Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:
Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, t.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, i.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy Majlisi qonunchilik palatasi deputati
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, i.f.n., professor, MIM akademiyasi rektori
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Ilmiy ishlar va innovatsiyalar bo'yicha prorektori
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, i.f.d., prof., Navoiy davlat pedagogika instituti rektori
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, p.f.f.d., (PhD), Buxoro muhandislik-texnologiya instituti rektori
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Hududiy ta'lim muassasalari va markazlar bo'yicha prorektor v.b.
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, i.f.d., TDIUprofessor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, i.f.n., TDIU professori
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, t.f.d., Rossiya xalqlar do'stligi universiteti professori
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, i.f.d., prof., Xalqaro "Nordik" universiteti rektori
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, i.f.d., TSUE professori
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farxod, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, f.f.d. profesor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, SamDu IS instituti professori
Cham Tat Huei, (PhD) USCI universiteti professori, Malayziya
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, i.f.d., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri o'rinbosari
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, i.f.f.d.,(PhD) "El-yurt umidi" jamg'armasi ijrochi direktori o'rinbosari
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, t.f.f.d.,(PhD) TAQU katta o'qituvchisi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich. v.b. dotsent (PhD)
Djudi Smetana, p.f.n., Pitsburg davlat universiteti dotsenti, Pittsburgh, Kansas, AQSH
Krissi Lyuis, p.f.n., Pitsburg davlat universiteti dotsenti, Pittsburgh, Kansas, AQSH
Ali Kopak (Али Кўнак), i.f.d., prof., Karabuk universiteti dotsenti, Turkiya
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, i.f.n., "LUKOIL-Energoservis" Kompaniyasi iqtisodchisi, Moskva.
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, i.f.f.d., (PhD) TDIU dotsenti
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, PhD, Turkiya Anqara universiteti doktoranti
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Oqil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjaevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, DSc, Prof., Minister of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Rae Kwon Chung, honorary professor of TSUE, Nobel laureate, South Korea,

Osman Mesten, member of the Turkish Parliament, head of the Turkey-Uzbekistan Friendship Society

Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, DSc, Prof., Deputy of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich CSc, Prof., Rector of Academy of Labor and Social Relations

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, DSc, Prof., TSUE Vice-Rector for Scientific Affairs and Innovation

Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhriddinovich, DSc, Prof., Rector of the Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Siddikova Sadokat Ghaforovna, PhD, Rector of the Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, DSc, Prof., acting Vice-rector for regional educational institutions and centers of TSUE

Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, CSc, Prof., of TSUE

Slizovsky Dimitriy Yegorovich, DSc, Prof., of the People's Friendship University of Russia

Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, DSc, Prof., Rector of International "Nordic" University

Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixov'ja ugli, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of the DGPO of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the DCECGPO of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Eshtayev Alisher Abduganievich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, PhD in Philology, Professor.

Shoira Azimovna Musaeva, professor of SamDu IS Institute

Cham Tat Huei, PhD, professor at USCI University, Malaysia

Buzrukkhanov Sarvarkhan Munavvarkhanovich, DSc, Deputy Minister of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, PhD, deputy of executive director of the "El-yurt umidi" fund

Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, PhD, Senior Lecturer at Tashkent University of Architecture and Construction

Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Acting Associate Professor (PhD)

Judy Smetana CSc, Associate Professor, Pittsburgh State University, Pittsburgh, Kansas, USA

Chrissy Lewis CSc, Associate Professor, Pittsburgh State University, Pittsburgh, Kansas, USA

Ali Konak DSc, Prof., Associate Professor of Karabuk University, Turkey

Glazova Marina Viktorovna, CSc, economist at LUKOIL-Energoservis Company, Moscow.

Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, associate professor of TSUE

Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, PhD, doctoral student at Ankara University, Turkey

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, independent researcher of TSUE

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, t.f.d., profesor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, f.f.d., TDIU professori
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, i. f. n., TDAU dotsenti
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, f.f.n., Farg'ona davlat universiteti dotsenti
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, i.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, p.f.f.d., (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, i.f.f.d. (PhD), Alfraganus universiteti dotsenti
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, i.f.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, i.f.d., TMI dotsenti
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich – Doctor of Technical Sciences, Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich – Doctor of Philosophy, Professor at TSUE
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich – Doctor of Philosophy, Professor at TSUE
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich – Candidate of Technical Sciences, Associate Professor at TSUA
Rustamov Ilhomiddin – Candidate of Technical Sciences, Associate Professor at Fergana State University
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich – Doctor of Philosophy, Associate Professor at TSUE
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna – Doctor of Philosophy, Associate Professor at TSUE
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Associate Professor at Alfraganus University
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Associate Professor at TSUE
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi – Doctor of Philosophy, Associate Professor at TSUE
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna – Senior Lecturer at TSUE
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna – Independent Researcher at TSUE

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Геоэкономические аспекты проекта железной дороги «Китай – Кыргызстан – Узбекистан»: вызовы и перспективы	18
О.К. Абдурахманов, А.С. Камалов	
Soliq to'lovchilar tomonidan soliqlarni yashirishni oldini olish masalalari	24
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich	
Moliyaviy xavfsizlik va iqtisodiy barqarorlik o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik	30
Axmedov Bezxod Shuxratovich	
To'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalarning iqtisodiyot taraqqiyotidagi roli	34
Mamatov Bahadir Safaralievich	
Milliy iqtisodiyotda xususiy sektorni rivojlantirishning mulk kapitallashuviga ta'siri	40
Norboyev Odil Abrayevich	
Возможные пути применения ии при подборе персонала в нефтегазовые компании Узбекистана	49
Эльбек Олимович Амирханов	
Sug'urta kompaniyalarida moliyaviy oqimlarni boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirish masalalari	53
Qarshiyev Otabek Abdullayevich	
Экономические предпосылки формирование социальных издержек как результат воздействия экологических факторов	57
Сеитова Лейла Пулатовна	
Геологические и гидродинамические аспекты месторождений углеводородов в зеленой экономике	68
Турдиев Шохжахон Шермадат угли	
Управление процессом снижения транзакционных издержек в условиях экологизации экономики	74
Ходжаева Нодирахон Абдурашидовна	
Yashil texnologiyalarga investitsiyalar – yashil iqtisodiyot istiqboli	79
Yuldashev Mutalib Ibrohimovich	
“Yashil iqtisodiyot”ga o'tish orqali barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlashning mintaqaviy jihatlari	83
Samiyeva Gulnoza Toxirovna	
Sotish jarayoni buxgalteriya hisobida moliyalashtirishning salmoqli komponenti va qaytarish huquqi	89
Sattorov Toxir Tolmas o'g'li	
Raqamli transformatsiya korxonalarining ishlab chiqarish samaradorligiga ta'siri	99
Vafoyeva Dilafruz Ikomovna	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarining media imiji va unga rakamli transformatsiyaning ta'siri	104
Nazarov G'ulom Akmal o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim tashkilotlarida xodimlar bilan ish haqi bo'yicha hisob-kitoblarni takomillashtirish	109
Abdumajitov Shaxobiddin Shamsiddin o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda yashil transport tizimiga o'tish bo'yicha amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar va rivojlantirishning istiqbollari	116
Yuldashev Farhodbek Abdumutalibovich	
Application of social media marketing in the world experience	120
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
Xitoyning ta'minot zanjirlarini boshqarish tajribasidan foydalanisafzalliklari	125
Hislatxonova Madinaxon Avazxon qizi, Abduraimova Azizaxon Dilmurod qizi, D.N.Ishmanova	
Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishda ishbilarmonlik muhitining moderator roli	130
Nasirxodjayeva Dilafruz Sabitxanovna, Abduvohidov Behzod xxx	

“Yoshlar daftari” loyihasi asosida daromadlilikni ta’minlash masalalari 136 Murodova Mohigul Chori qizi, Baxromov Umidjon Ulug’bek o’g’li	136
Основопологающие принципы разработки концепции конкурентоспособности страховых компаний 143 Азимжон Мелиев Муродулло угли	143
Формирование инклюзивных психологических процессов под влиянием эзотерических факторов..... 148 Исаев Кобилжон Абдукодирович	148
Foyda soliqlari (12-son bhxs) buxgalteriya hisobining xalqaro standartini respublikamiz amaliyotiga transformasiya qilishdagi vazifalar..... 153 Rizaev Xushnud Namazovich	153
Iqtisodiy tizimda budjet daromadlarini shakllanishining ilmiy-nazariy va konseptual asoslarining ahamiyati..... 158 Yusupov Ruslan	158
Biriktirilgan va tartibga soluvchi soliqlarni taqsimlashning xorijiy davlatlar tajribasi tahlili 165 Turotova Nigora Xolmurod qizi	165

APPLICATION OF SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING IN THE WORLD EXPERIENCE

Musayeva Shoira Azimovna

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service,
Usmanova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna

Associate professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service

Abstract: This article discusses the importance of social media marketing, identifying effective strategies for brand development in manufacturing enterprises, ways to take advantage of digital platforms, and future approaches. The use of social media marketing in production enterprises is considered in the world experience.

Key words: social media marketing, digital strategies, brand image, performance, competition, brand development.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ijtimoiy media marketingining ahamiyati, ishlab chiqarish korxonalarida brendni rivojlantirish uchun samarali strategiyalarni aniqlash, raqamli platformalarning imkoniyatlaridan foydalanish usullari va istiqboldagi yondashuvlar muhokama qilingan. Ishlab chiqarish korxonalarida ijtimoiy media marketingini jahon tajribasida qo'llanilishi ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ijtimoiy media marketingi, raqamli strategiyalar, brend imiji, samaradorlik, raqobat, brend rivojlantirish.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается важность маркетинга в социальных сетях, определяются эффективные стратегии развития бренда на производственных предприятиях, способы использования преимуществ цифровых платформ и будущие подходы. Рассмотрен мировой опыт использования маркетинга в социальных сетях на производственных предприятиях.

Ключевые слова: маркетинг в социальных сетях, цифровые стратегии, имидж бренда, производительность, конкуренция, развитие бренда.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, social media marketing (SMM) is becoming one of the most effective tools for manufacturing companies to promote their products and services. The digitization policy conducted in our country has opened the door to wide opportunities in this field. Many businesses are using SMM strategies to promote their brands globally.

In order to successfully operate in the market, it is important for companies to be in close contact with their customers, to promote their products in modern and interactive ways. Social media platforms serve not only as an effective tool in this process, but also as an opportunity to increase competitiveness.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The application of social media marketing (SMM) has become an indispensable part of global business strategies. Scholars and researchers have extensively analyzed the role of SMM in driving brand awareness, customer engagement, and sales growth. This review synthesizes findings from prominent studies, highlighting their contributions to the understanding of social media marketing's global impact.

Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) provided a foundational framework for understanding social media platforms, classifying them into six categories based on social presence and media richness. They emphasized the importance of leveraging these platforms to create meaningful connections with consumers, laying the groundwork for strategic SMM practices.

Mangold and Faulds (2009) argued that social media represents a hybrid element of the promotion mix, where traditional advertising principles intersect with customer-to-customer interactions. Their work underscores

the necessity for businesses to integrate SMM into broader marketing strategies to maintain competitiveness in the digital age.

Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick (2019) explored practical approaches to SMM, identifying key performance indicators (KPIs) such as engagement rates, click-through rates (CTRs), and conversion metrics. Their research offers actionable insights for businesses to measure the effectiveness of SMM campaigns across different industries.

More recently, Felix, Rauschnabel, and Hinsch (2017) proposed a comprehensive framework for strategic SMM, focusing on four dimensions: scope, culture, structure, and governance. Their model emphasizes the importance of aligning social media activities with organizational objectives, ensuring consistency and coherence in brand messaging.

In the context of global SMM practices, Kietzmann et al. (2011) introduced the “honeycomb model,” which highlights seven functional building blocks of social media: identity, conversations, sharing, presence, relationships, reputation, and groups. Their framework provides a robust tool for marketers to design targeted campaigns that resonate with diverse audiences.

Zhu and Chen (2015) investigated the role of cultural differences in shaping SMM strategies, illustrating that successful campaigns often adapt to local values and preferences. For instance, their analysis of global brands like Coca-Cola and Nike demonstrated how culturally tailored messaging can significantly enhance campaign effectiveness.

The impact of influencer marketing as part of SMM has also been a focus of recent studies. Lou and Yuan (2019) found that authenticity and relatability are critical factors driving consumer trust and purchase intentions in influencer-led campaigns. This insight highlights the evolving dynamics of SMM, where consumers value genuine interactions over overtly promotional content.

While social media offers unparalleled opportunities for engagement, researchers such as Tuten and Solomon (2018) caution against potential pitfalls, including privacy concerns, over-commercialization, and the risk of reputational damage from poorly managed campaigns. They recommend adopting ethical practices and transparency to build long-term customer trust.

From the author’s perspective, these studies collectively illustrate the evolving complexity of social media marketing. They highlight not only its benefits but also the challenges that businesses must navigate. By synthesizing these insights, practitioners can craft more effective and adaptive marketing strategies in the ever-changing digital landscape.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research used a systematic approach, marketing analysis, comparison and evaluation of numerical indicators. Crowd tracking techniques were used to collect and analyze data from social media platforms.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The main objective of the study is to study the role and strategies of social media marketing in brand development in manufacturing enterprises. To achieve this goal, the following tasks were solved:

1. Analysis of the importance of SMM principles in brand development.
2. Development of effective SMM strategies for enterprises.
3. Evaluation of the economic efficiency of using different platforms.

Opportunities for social media platforms

Enterprises’ SMM effectiveness often depends on how they use the platforms. For example:

Table 1. Effectiveness of social media platforms.

Platforms	Private assets	Target audience	Efficiency
Facebook	Wide audience, advertising segmentation	Older users	Good for communication and brand recognition
Instagram	Visual content, creative advertising	Young people, creative and fashion lovers	Image creation and product promotion
Linkedin	Professional communication and networking	Business and corporate customers	Convenient for B2B marketing
Tiktok	Short video, high interactivity	Young audience, trend watchers	Popularity

Table 6. Comparison of SMM economic performance across the US, Germany and India:

Indicators	USA(2023)	Germany(2022)	India(2024)
Brand recognition rate(%)	78	72	70
Expenditure on SMM (million)	\$13,800	€6,800	RUB 110.00
Sales through SMM	\$210,000	€100,000	1,900,000 ra
SMM benefit	\$75,000	€40,000	700,000 ra

These data show how the SMM strategy adapts to the economic conditions of the countries. For example, in India, SMM costs are high because of its large population, but this investment has yielded huge returns. In Germany, however, SMM costs were relatively low, but efficiency was high.

The main drivers of economic benefits from social media marketing have been:

1. Interactivity: If the level of interaction of the content with the user is high, the volume of sales will increase rapidly.

2. Innovative approach: The use of SMM technologies and AI tools has increased the effectiveness of brands.

3. Competitive environment: In countries where competition is fierce, brands are spending more and gaining efficiency.

Sectoral analysis of economic efficiency of SMM is important. The table below provides an analysis of examples from the technology, fashion and food industries:

Table 7. Analysis of economic efficiency of SMM by specific sectors.

Sector	SMM expenses (million)	SMM profit (million)	Efficiency(%)
Technology	20,000	80,000	400
Fashion	10,000	40,000	400
Food	5,000	25,000	500

As can be seen from this table, the food industry has achieved the highest efficiency from SMM, as this sector requires the promotion of products closer to consumers. In the technology and fashion sectors, an innovative approach was a priority. Regional differences in SMM development

The effectiveness of SMM development varies significantly across geographic regions. For example:

- North America: Expansion of SMM tools, targeted ads, and artificial intelligence integration are the major growth drivers of the market.

- Europe: Emphasis is placed on integration into the SMM technologies and ecosystem, which helps optimize ad spend.

- Asia and Africa: Large populations and low competitive environment present huge opportunities for SMM.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Social media marketing has emerged as a transformative force in the global business environment, providing innovative ways for companies to engage with their audiences, enhance brand visibility, and drive revenue growth. This study demonstrates that SMM is not merely an auxiliary tool but a core component of modern marketing strategies, demanding careful planning, execution, and evaluation.

The literature reveals several critical themes. First, the integration of social media into traditional marketing frameworks has opened new opportunities for two-way communication and community building. Second, the effectiveness of SMM lies in its adaptability to diverse cultural contexts, as seen in the success of global brands employing localized strategies. Third, the rise of influencer marketing and advanced analytics tools underscores the need for authenticity, data-driven decision-making, and ethical practices to maintain customer trust and loyalty.

Despite its vast potential, social media marketing is not without challenges. Privacy concerns, rapid technological advancements, and the need for constant innovation place considerable demands on businesses. However, these challenges also present opportunities for companies to differentiate themselves by staying ahead of trends, adopting transparent practices, and fostering meaningful customer relationships.

In conclusion, the global experience of SMM offers valuable lessons for practitioners and academics alike. By leveraging the frameworks and insights provided by scholars, businesses can navigate the complexities of social media platforms and create impactful campaigns that resonate with their target audiences. Moving forward, continued research into emerging technologies, cultural dynamics, and consumer behavior will be essential to unlocking the full potential of social media marketing.

List of used literature

1. Mirziyoev Sh.M. Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rule of every leader's activity. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2017.- 104 p.
2. Mirziyoev Sh.M. The rule of law and protection of human interests are the guarantee of the country's development and people's well-being. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2017.- 48 p.
3. Mirziyoev Sh.M. We will build a great future with our brave and noble people. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2017.- 488 p.
4. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. January 24, 2020. - People's Speech, January 26, 2020.
5. Decree No. PF-4947 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
6. Asian Development Bank. (2021). Sustainable Transport Initiative: Achieving Low-Carbon and Inclusive Growth in Asia. Retrieved from www.adb.org.
7. International Monetary Fund. (2022). World Economic Outlook: Recovery Amid Uncertainty. Washington, DC: IMF.
8. Litman, T. (2020). Evaluating Public Transit Benefits and Costs: Best Practices Guidebook. Victoria Transport Policy Institute. Retrieved from www.vtpi.org.
9. Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs, Government of India. (2023). Annual Report on Metro Rail Development. New Delhi: Government of India.
10. OECD. (2022). The Economic Benefits of Public Transport Investments. Paris: OECD Publishing.
11. Smith, A., & Krogstad, E. (2021). Urban Mobility and Sustainable Growth in Developing Countries. *Journal of Urban Studies*, 58(3), 456–478.
12. UN-Habitat. (2020). Enhancing Urban Mobility: Sustainable Transport Solutions for Cities. Nairobi: United Nations Human Settlements Programme.
13. World Bank. (2021). Transforming Cities with Mass Transit: Lessons from Global Metro Systems. Washington, DC: The World Bank Group.
14. Musaeva Sh. A. Marketing research. Textbook «STAR-SEL» LLC publishing and creative department. Samarkand-2023
15. Musaeva Sh. A. Integrated marketing communication Study guide "Mahorat" publishing house, Samarkand -
16. 2022.
17. Musaeva Sh. A., Usmonova DI Innovative marketing "TURON EDITION" study guide for 2021.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokr ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2024. № 12

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.

Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77)

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77) telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

